

Identification of 4Q56 (4QIsa^b) Fragments, Addition (PAM 43.664 frag. 10)

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I recently reported in *Revue de Qumran* on the identification of seven 4Q56 fragments,¹ three from the plates of unidentified fragments which were published in DJD 33,² one from PAM 43.398, already identified earlier by me,³ and three other ones which were included in the edition of 4Q56, but not yet identified with regard to their text.⁴ Given the large number of tiny hitherto unidentified fragments, especially those on the plates of DJD 33, more 4Q56 fragments may still be waiting for identification.

One such fragment is PAM 43.664 frag. 10,⁵ which should be placed very closely (less than 1 mm) to the left of PAM 43.398 frag. 9 which preserved Isa 55:12-56:1.

The join of the two fragments now reads:

1.6. PAM 43.398 frag. 9 [4Q56 frag. 48] + PAM 43.664 frag. 10 [4Q56 frag. 48a] / Isa 55:12-56:2 / one revolution of the scroll further than 4Q56 frag. 39

ובשלו]ם	1
[כף תחת הַנְּעֻצוֹ]ץ	2
[עולם לא] יִכְרַת]	3
ק[רוב]ה] יִשׁוּ]עתי	4
יחזי]ק ב]ה	5

¹Eibert Tigchelaar, "Identification of 4Q56 (4QIsa^b) Fragments," *RevQ* 31/114 (2019): 275-81

²Tigchelaar, "Identification," 1.1; 1.2; and 1.3.

³Tigchelaar, "Identification," 1.6. Earlier transcriptions: Tigchelaar, "Minuscule Qumranica I," *RevQ* 21/84 (2004): 643-48, at 646; and Tigchelaar, "Publication of PAM 43.398 (IAA #202) Including New Fragments of 4Q269," in *From 4QMMT to Resurrection: Mélanges qumraniens en hommage à Émile Puech*, ed. Florentino García Martínez, Annette Steudel, and Eibert Tigchelaar (Leiden: Brill, 2006), 265-80, at 270.

⁴Patrick W. Skehan and Eugene Ulrich, "56. 4QIsa^b," in Eugene Ulrich et al., *Qumran Cave 4, X: The Prophets*, Discoveries in the Judaean Desert 15 (Oxford: Clarendon, 1997), 19-43, frags. 46, 38, 43; Tigchelaar, "identification," 1.4; 1.5; and 1.7.

⁵Cf. Dana M. Pike and Andrew C. Skinner, *Qumran Cave 4, XXIII: Unidentified Fragments*, Discoveries in the Judaean Desert 33 (Oxford: Clarendon, 2001), 26 and Pl. V. See also the new infra-red image on <https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-493752>.